

FEATURES OF THE COMMUNICATION SPHERE OF PSYCHOLOGIST STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the features of the communicative sphere of students - future psychologists. The peculiarity of the communicative sphere of students is its variability in the learning process in an educational institution.*

Keywords: *communication; sociability; empathy; communicative sphere of personality; features of communicative sphere of students majoring in psychology.*

During periods of intense change in the economic and political life of society, there is always an increased interest in the problem of the main driving forces of human life, in the possibilities of adapting the individual to the social environment surrounding him. The issues of the formation, development and functioning of the human communicative sphere are directly related to the problems of communication, interpersonal interaction and professional relations. The communicative sphere of personality is becoming one of the most important subjects of study in modern psychological science.

At present, it is important to study personal communicative characteristics that determine the organization of a person's interpersonal space and its adaptation in a social environment. A significant difficulty in solving this problem is the construction of universal explanatory and corrective models for the development of communicative personality traits.

Based on the studies of the communicative sphere of students (G.V.Akopov, A.A.Bodalev, A.G.Kovalev, T.V.Semenova, I.P.Shkuratova and others), self-determination of students (M.A. Bilan, P.S.Gurevich, V.Yu.Doroshenko, L.I.Zotova, A.G.Karayani, V.N.Lavrinenko, A.N.Leontiev, B.L.Yashin and others) [4], we determined the purpose of the study: to study the characteristics of the communicative sphere of students - future psychologists. The issues of development of the communicative sphere of the individual are extremely important in the system of professional training of students. It is at the initial stage of "mastering" a profession during training at a university that a young person is self-determined in life, his life and worldview positions are formed, individual methods and techniques of his activity, behavior and communication are mastered. The communicative sphere is professionally significant for psychology students. The relevance of the topic is due to the importance of the process of communication in the professional activities of a psychologist. The totality of professional and personal qualities that make up the communicative sphere of a psychologist reflects the level of his professional readiness and maturity, determines the prospects for the personal development of future specialists, the success of their professional activities.

Communication is a complex and multifaceted process. According to A.A.Bodalev, this is the interaction of people, the content of which is the exchange of information using various means of communication to establish relationships between people [1].

According to A.A.Leontiev, communication is the process of establishing and maintaining purposeful, direct and mediated by one or another means of contact between people, one way or another psychologically connected with each other [1].

B.D.Parygin notes that the process of communication can act at the same time as a process of interaction between people, and as an information process, and as the attitude of people to each other, and as a process of mutual influence, experience and understanding of each other [2] .

Perception and understanding of a person by a person is the most important stage of communication and building relationships. The attitude towards another person, the desire or unwillingness to continue communication with him depends on our perception and interpretation of appearance, character traits, motives of actions. Perception depends on the installation on people in general, on a specific group or person. The installation is directly influenced by our personal experience of communication, relationships; experience and instructions of people who are authoritative for us (first of all, parents, relatives, close people); information coming from the media and books. In addition to setting, perception is influenced by our self-esteem, self-concept, ideas about ourselves in comparison with other people. An important influence on our perception is exerted by social stereotypes - schematic, standard images of a particular group of people formed by society [3]. As a result of the perception and understanding of a person, an attitude towards him is formed, supported emotionally.

An integral part of the interaction is interpersonal relationships - objectively experienced, to varying degrees, perceived relationships between people. They are based on a variety of emotional states of interacting people and their psychological characteristics. Emotional relationships appear in the form of likes and dislikes of one person for another. In their development, they pass through a system of filters, which are characterized by an increasing consideration of the features of the inner world of another person [4].

The main function of communication is influence, which can be carried out in the form of persuasion or suggestion. Persuasion is the process of logically substantiating a judgment in order to achieve a shift in the mind of the interlocutor. Suggestion is a process of influence designed for an uncritical perception of reality: something is asserted without evidence; the main role is played by the credibility of the source of information. When choosing a method of influence, it is necessary to take into account the suggestibility of a person.

Student youth is a significant part of modern Russian society. With a high level of education, active working age, dynamic social behavior, it forms the main intellectual and productive layer of society. By actively implementing their aspirations and goals, young people largely set the vector for the future development of modern society. She has the ability to process and assimilate a large amount of information, which, in turn, forms the ability of a young person to find original ways to solve difficult issues. Young people are actively developing the communicative sphere of personality. This is due to finding and establishing new social connections, as well as the high need of young people for dynamic interpersonal communication [3]. Each group of students studying in a particular university has its own living conditions (learning and communication, work and life), features of social behavior and a system of value orientations [4].

One of the main functions of interpersonal communication in a group is the development of mutually acceptable solutions, the elimination of contradictions that give rise to hostility and intransigence - that is, the group achieves unification on the basis of common agreements and mutual concessions.

Empathy is the ability to empathize, emotional perception of another person, penetration into the inner world of another, acceptance of all his thoughts and feelings. K. Rogers defined

empathy as a special relationship that includes several aspects: entry into the world of experiences of another person and free orientation in it; subtle sensitivity to the changing processes in this world; living the “other person's life” is delicate, not judgmental, not trying to discover more than the person is willing to reveal, and at the same time helping to make this experience more complete. Empathy is the most important condition for a person's personal development [1].

To assess sociability and sociability, the test of V.F.Ryakhovsky was chosen. Sociability is the ability to establish contacts, the ability to communicate constructively and mutually enriching with other people. Sociability is one of the skills of successful social interaction and affects both professional and personal spheres of communication [2]. It is one of the important personal qualities of people whose profession involves active direct communication with others.

The professional activity of a psychologist involves conducting conversations, interviews. For its successful implementation, knowledge about the communicative sphere of the individual, good communication skills, the ability to establish interpersonal relationships, identify the most significant elements of interpersonal communication and creatively apply them, win over people are required. The psychologist must have formed a correct, non-judgmental perception of other people. Therefore, the formation of the skill of effective interpersonal communication in future psychologists is essential.

Important aspects of interpersonal communication include: communicative competence, that is, a developing and conscious experience of communication between people, sociability, contact, initiative, communicative and speech activity. The presence of developed communication skills makes it easy to communicate and establish contact. Such skills include the ability to listen, speak out to the place, maintain a conversation, choose the correct form of address to the interlocutor. Contact is another important aspect in the ability to communicate. This social skill is based on natural sociability and the ability to enter into psychological contact, to form trusting relationships based on mutual acceptance in the course of communication.

Thus, future psychologists need not only to acquire professional knowledge, skills and competencies, but also to develop the communicative sphere, interpersonal communication skills. The solution of these problems actualizes the development and implementation in the educational process of new methods for the development of the communicative sphere of students and the formation of their interpersonal communication skills.

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